

range 9 airline km southeast of closest reported locality at Cerro Petlalcala, Municipality of San Andrés Tenejapan, Veracruz, México (De La Torre-Loranca et al. 2002. *Herpetol. Rev.* 33:215). The snake was observed thermoregulating on a trail near the Tekilatlakpan Ecotourism Center. The vegetation is a mature acahual of *Pinus* sp. planted ca. 20 years ago. We thank Neftalí Camacho for cataloging the photograph and Luis Canseco-Márquez for species verification.

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TANTILLA CORONATA (Southeastern Crowned Snake). USA: VIRGINIA: BOTETOURT Co.: Carvin's Cove Natural Reserve (37.39040°N, 80.00950°W; WGS 84). 15 July 2022. Verified by Jessica Grady. David H. Snyder Museum of Zoology, Austin Peay State University (APSU 20157; photo voucher). We found the snake in the soil ca. 5 cm underground while digging to install a drift fence. New county record (Virginia Fish and Wildlife Information Service. <https://vafwis.dgif.virginia.gov/fwis/>, 9 March 2023). The nearest known vouchered locality is ca. 57.3 km to the southeast in Pittsylvania County (south of Smith Mountain; National Museum of Natural History, Smithsonian Institution [USNM] 145428).

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THAMNOPHIS ROSSMANI (Rossmann's Gartersnake). MEXICO: NAYARIT: MUNICIPIO DE SANTA MARÍA DEL ORO: 1.3 km NW La Labor (21.37706°N, 104.73037°W; WGS 84), 1056 m elev. 18 August 2012. E. Arcadia-Moreno and S. Figueroa-Acosta. Verified by Christoph Grünwald. Amphibian and Reptile Diversity Research Center, The University of Texas at Arlington (UTADC 10052; photo voucher). Habitat at point of observation comprises two retention ponds within a broader matrix of agricultural fields

and low, seasonally flooded pastureland. This aligns well with our knowledge of the species, which is apparently associated with lentic and first-order lotic habitats, including marshlands, ditches, springs, and seepage runs. New municipality record (Conant 2000. *Occas. Pap. Mus. Nat. Sci.* 76:1–7; Loc-Barragan et al. 2024. *Herpetozoa* 37:25–42). The nearest published record was taken ca. 15 km to the northwest, at “3 km S of Pantanal”, Municipio de Xalisco (Luja and Grünwald 2015. *Herpetol. Rev.* 46:223–225). This species is restricted to the upper Río Mololóa (= “Río San Cayetano”) drainage of south-central Nayarit and remains poorly known. We thank T.D. Schramer for reviewing the language of this note, and G. G. Pandelis for cataloging the voucher photograph.

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TRIMERESURUS SALAZAR (Salazar's Pit Viper). INDIA: UTTARAKHAND: Nainital District: Kishanpur Forest Range, Dauli Khatta (29.06783°N, 79.61522°E; WGS 84), ca. 260 m elev. 6 October 2022. Jignasu Dolia. Verified by Ashok Captain. Lee Kong Chian Natural History Museum, National University of Singapore (ZRC [IMG] 2.693a–d; photo voucher). First record from Uttarakhand. This new locality is ca. 491 km from nearest published locality in Chitwan National Park, Nepal (Vogel et al. 2022. *Zootaxa* 5175:343–366). We thank Ministry of Environment, Forests and Climate Change, Govt. of India, for funding under the National Mission on Himalayan Studies, G.N. Chaniyal for providing information, S. Haldar, K. D. Tiwari, Y. Singh, and B. S. Bonal for fieldwork assistance.

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